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MENTAL HEALTH IN NURSING PRECEPTORS: STRATEGIES FOR HEALTH PROMOTION

AUTHORS

Camila Cristina Rodrigues: Master's degree in Semiotics, Information Technology and Education, Nurse and Educator. PhD candidate in Public Health - UNIDA University

Contact: profcamilacristinarodrigues@gmail.com | +55(11)97321-0293

Ricardo De Bonis: Doctor of Business Administration from Universidad Americana – PY, Dental Surgeon, President of the iiEP Institute, Professor of the subject “Ethics in Academic Production” at Universidad UNIDA.

Contact: ricardo@debonis.com.br | +55(21)98799-6653

ABSTRACT

Mental health is an essential component of well-being and takes on particular relevance in care-centered professions, such as nursing. Preceptors, responsible for guiding the practical training of new professionals, experience demands that can compromise their emotional balance, including work overload and compassion fatigue. This study aims to analyze, in the literature, the mental health of nursing preceptors and identify health promotion strategies aimed at this population. This is a qualitative, descriptive study. The results point to factors associated with illness, such as double shifts, insufficient institutional support, and a scarcity of resources for psychological care. These conditions reinforce the need for initiatives that promote well-being, including support programs, spaces for qualified listening, and training actions for stress management. It is concluded that investing in the mental health of preceptors strengthens pedagogical practice and the training of future nurses.

Keywords: Mental Health. Preceptor. Nursing. Strategies.Promotion.